

**XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI**
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**THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL MANAGEMENT IN THE EDUCATIONAL
PROCESS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN
LANGUAGE TEACHING**

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Annotation: *The purpose of this article is to discuss and determine the importance of management of pedagogy in teaching process and the efficiency of artificial intelligence programmes in learning language. In this article, we will learn wider definition of pedagogical management. Also, the information about some ways of pedagogical management and source of artificial intelligence in teaching language will be given.*

Keywords: *developed, education, foreign languages, artificial intelligence, pedagogical management, strengthening.*

Introduction

Today, we all know that there are developed, developing and lagging countries in the world. Day by day, all countries are developing various innovations and technologies as if they are competing with each other. The aspects that develop the country are sports, tourism, education, art. If the above-mentioned three types of countries increase their activities in these fields, no one will be able to compete with developed countries and if the developing ones increase their achievements regarding these fields, they can easily join the ranks of the developed countries, while those that have stopped civilization will begin to develop gradually. We may pay attention to the field of education, which has a great contribution to the development of every country. Strengthening education can be said to reinforce the consciousness of the nation. We should be concerned about how to promote education and how to engage society, especially, young people in education. There are several ways to strengthen education among society individuals. If they want to make their country improve in educational fields people should learn plenty of foreign languages, maths, physics, IT and other special subjects. First of all, we should teach kids because it will have efficiency since children have fresh brain in order to learn new things quickly rather than older people who have more concerns about life issues that overcome thoughts

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

of education. If we managed to engage children to learn new foreign languages it would be great opportunity to strengthen the education in the society. Because by learning foreign languages, we can acquire a more significant and stronger source of knowledge in other languages. Therefore, we always need the best pedagogical management ways in fields of education and well-organized technologies like artificial intelligence in teaching languages.

Definiton of pedagogical management. Pedagogical management refers to the strategic planning, implementation, organization and evaluation of teaching-learning process. It ensures that educational institutions operate efficiently, educators receive proper training and students achieve their learning objectives. Thus, the quality of education is measured by the quality of the teaching process, highlighting the importance of the teacher's professional, ethical, and moral training. Proper training is crucial for the development of effective PM (pedagogical management) and for enhancing learning outcomes.¹ Pedagogical management is a special kind of activities of all subjects of the educational process aimed at achieving goals and using the forms and methods for facilitating its functioning and development as a pedagogical system [1]. According to Talyzina's research, pedagogical management is inextricably linked with certain effects, necessary for the implementation of target criteria of the educational process: maintenance within established boundaries (functioning) or transition to a new state (development). According to the authors this type of management is aimed at regulating the educational process in order to transfer it to a higher level [2]².

The role of pedagogical management in education process. There are several key functions of this management. First of all, teachers should design structured learning programs aligned with educational goals. It would be useful both teachers and learners since it is planned. Moreover, it is important to ensure that educators are equipped with modern teaching methodologies which show teacher's training and development. If methodologies are old-fashioned they can not help students to improve equally with developed countries' learners. In order to have efficiency of the management teachers must possess student-centered learning approaches by promoting active and interactive learning experiences. It means that students should

¹ <https://www.researchgate.net/>

² <https://elib.bsu.by/bitstream/>

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

be given more active tasks to do independently rather than relying on or listening to the teacher. Implementing feedback mechanisms to measure student progress plays a significant role since by learning from mistakes is more efficient in order not make such mistakes anymore. Furthermore, teachers should ensure to enhance learning experiences through digital tools and artificial intelligence-based solutions. As we are living in life growing with cutting-edge technologies we should be aware of how to utilize them. Unfortunately, many schools in rural areas or developing countries lack adequate access to the technology or learning materials necessary to support innovative learning approaches[3]. Of special importance here, is pedagogical competence, the aspect of professional competence which comprises general pedagogical knowledge (GPK) as well as the skill to transform knowledge into performance (situation-specific skills). GPK, along with content knowledge (CK) and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), is one aspect of professional knowledge that is particularly relevant for teaching and is, therefore, frequently examined[4].

The Role of AI Technologies in Language Teaching. First and foremost, AI-powered tools provide personalized and efficient ways to teach and learn languages by automating processes, offering real-time feedback and creating interactive learning environments. Learning new language with the help of artificial intelligence is more easy and enjoyable. Due to the fact that new learners do not have to worry about making mistake while studying new things since artificial intelligence technologies do not have function that can make fun of or laugh at unconscious people like some individuals who tend to tease beginners in new field. Moreover, it is not difficult to find other benefits of artificial intelligence. As it mentioned above this type of technologies include personalized learning paths. That is, AI adapts to individual learning styles and proficiency levels. With it's help people can feel safety while using it. Learners can practice anytime, anywhere since these technologies have 24/7 accessibility which is more necessary side of them. Users do not have to wait for feedbacks for a long period owing to the fact that AI provides instant corrections and suggestions immediately. Most of artificial intelligence technologies consist of gamification and interactive AI-powered exercises that can enhance motivation. These means can always increase the engagement between learners and AI-powered exercises. In general, AI is intended to execute and facilitate human tasks virtually. This concept can benefit both teachers and students in the teaching and learning process when it is used in a learning environment[5].

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

There are number of applicants for AI in teaching language. For instance, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS). AI-based systems like Duolingo and Rosetta Stone provide customized lessons based on individual progress. It is worth mention that Duolingo has majority of users worldwide. Tools such as Google Translate and ChatGPT assist with language comprehension, pronunciation and translation. It is called natural language processing (NLP). Another applicants are speech recognition and pronunciation tools. According to Rusmiyanto et al. (2023), AI technologies such as speech recognition and virtual instructors can help students practice and improve their speaking and pronunciation abilities[6]

AI is having a significant impact on many areas of education, including teaching English as a second language (ELT). AI-powered tools and technologies improve students' learning experiences, personalize learning, and provide immediate feedback at all grade levels.

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Applicants like Chatbots and Virtual Assistants enable real-time conversation practice with instant feedback. AI has automated assessments and feedback. Therefore, AI-driven evaluation systems can analyze grammar, fluency, vocabulary in speaking and writing. In recent research, the Lyra Virtual Assistant (LVA) was used. This program is an intelligent personal assistant that responds to queries from users on a variety of subjects, offers suggestions, and manages the user's device using natural language[7]. The results demonstrated that speaking teaching using Lyra Virtual Assistant produced better results for the experimental group than for the control group. Therefore, Lyra helps students perform better when speaking English.³ Talking about another important English skill, like writing, it can mention that there are many AI tools that play an essential role in English language teaching and learning, such as Grammarly. It is an award-winning online grammar-checking tool available for free and the most widely used in the world. In this sense, Vo et al., (2023) researched the use of Grammarly as a proofreader and the improvement in students' writing skills[8]. Automated writing evaluation (AWE) tools such as Grammarly or Write & Improve are software systems designed to assess and improve

³<https://ciencialatina.org/index.php/cienciala/article/download/7368/11111/>

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

writing skills by providing immediate feedback on a range of writing aspects, including grammar, punctuation, spelling, and syntax. Their particular benefit is their ability to offer ondemand, personalised feedback across multiple submissions within seconds, a level not achievable by teachers alone. A recent review paper found that AWE tools can have a positive impact on writing quality and accuracy, under certain circumstances [9]. AWE tools are considered useful for self-study when compared to learners receiving no feedback⁴. While not developed with educational purposes in mind, intelligent personal assistants (IPAs) such as Alexa or Google Assistant have also been explored in the context of language learning as conversational agents.⁵ Research shows that real-time interactivity in the context of task-based and cooperative activities can allow learners to engage in authentic communication, and therefore facilitates development of speaking skills [10]. Moreover, as with other types of AI agents, IPAs contribute to a positive learning environment by serving as non-threatening conversational partners, which is important for reducing learners' anxiety and increasing their communicative confidence [11].

Conclusion

In conclusion, pedagogical management plays a fundamental role in structuring and enhancing education process, ensuring that teaching techniques are effective and aligned with learners' needs. At the same time, Artificial Intelligence technologies have revolutionized language teaching by providing innovative, adaptive and engaging learning experiences. We have learnt and discussed some ways and results of pedagogical management and artificial intelligence in this article. Despite having problems with management in pedagogy while adapting to technological advancements, addressing diverse learning needs, managing resources effectively, ensuring continuous professional development for educators we should implement the several effective management methods in education process. Because it is clear that pedagogical management will be beneficial both teachers and students. If we go step by step and with clever plan towards our goals we will get our destination more easily and more earlier. It strikes me that even if it is necessary those methods can require the involvement of the government with financial or practical support. As we already know, applying artificial intelligence technologies can cause some issues as well. For example, AI lacks the emotional intelligence of human teachers. That

⁴ <https://www.cambridge.org/sites/>

⁵ <https://www.cambridge.org/sites/>

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

is, they cannot give us the proper emotions that we expect like sympathy, happiness, sadness, madness. Due to dependence on technology we may lose our critical thinking skills because we rely on AI too much. We always think these AI technologies include all true opinions and Another problem with using AI is accuracy issues. AI translations and speech recognition are not always perfect, especially in other languages rather than English like Uzbek, Russian. Since AI tools collect personal data the majority people may make raise ethical concerns. Owing to those challenges some individuals might doubt to utilise AI technologies. However, we need to trust them as they give us variation of opportunities, especially in learning new languages working with them is much more beneficial. Therefore, we must accept such management skills AI technologies in educational field.

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